

Analysis of Patterns in TV Commercials That Recognize NGO Image

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Abstract : The purpose of this research is to analyze the pattern of television commercials and how they encourage non-governmental organizations to build their image in Thailand. It realizes how public relations can impact an organization's image. It is a truth that bad public relations management can cause hurt a reputation. On the other hand, a very small amount of work in public relations helps your organization to be recognized broadly and eventually accepted even wider. The main idea in this paper is to study and analyze patterns of television commercials that could impact non-governmental organization's images in a greater way. This research uses questionnaires and content analysis to summarize results. The findings show the aspects of how patterns of television commercials that are suited to non-governmental organization work in Thailand. It will be useful for any non-governmental organization that wishes to build their image through television commercials and also for further work based on this research.

Keywords : television commercial (TVC), organization image, non-governmental organization (NGO), public relation

Conference Title : ICCFMS 2014 : International Conference on Communication, Film and Media Sciences

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : May 26-27, 2014